

Pediatric Neuromyelitis Optica Spectrum Disorder: A Case Report.

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ABSTRACT:

INTRODUCTION: Neuromyelitis Optica Spectrum Disorder (NMOSD), an autoimmune disorder of the central nervous system, was previously thought to be a subtype of multiple sclerosis (MS) due to shared symptoms like recurrent optic neuritis and spinal cord lesions. However, the identification of its specific antigen led to its recognition as a distinct disorder. Although NMOSD typically manifests between the ages of 25 to 40, occasional cases have been observed in children. **CASE REPORT:** We describe a case of a 14-year-old girl with three episodes of transient weakness in extremities involving different limbs during each presentation. This case underscores the difficulties in diagnosing, choosing the best treatment, and the importance of clear pediatric guidelines for diagnosing, treating, and preventing relapses in pediatric NMOSD. **DISCUSSION:** Children diagnosed with NMOSD tend to be older than those with acute disseminated encephalomyelitis (ADEM) but have a similar age range to those with MS. Additionally, they have a poorer prognosis compared to MS patients, according to Tillema et al. In a significant study at the Mayo Clinic, pediatric NMOSD patients had a median onset age of 12 years (range 4–18), with a notable female predominance (88%) and diverse ethnic backgrounds. **CONCLUSION:** additional research on the long-term safety and effectiveness of these newer treatments is crucial, especially for seronegative patients. While NMOSD occurrence in children is less frequent than in adults and mainly documented through case reports in the Indian subcontinent, further molecular investigations are essential to accurately differentiate it from other childhood autoimmune disorders.

INTRODUCTION

Neuromyelitis Optica Spectrum Disorder (NMOSD), an autoimmune disorder of the central nervous system, was previously thought to be a subtype of multiple sclerosis (MS) due to shared symptoms like recurrent optic neuritis and spinal cord lesions. However, the identification of its specific antigen led to its recognition as a distinct disorder.^[1] Although NMOSD typically manifests between the ages of 25 to 40, occasional cases have been observed in children. While pediatric demyelinating disorders share clinical features, the presence of AQP4 autoantibodies distinguishes NMOSD. Understanding the specific molecular events following autoantibody binding to AQP4 is an ongoing research area, particularly in pediatric cases within the Indian population, aiding in the differentiation from conditions like acute disseminated encephalomyelitis (ADEM).^[2]

CASE REPORT

We describe a case of a 14-year-old girl with three episodes of transient weakness in extremities involving different limbs during each presentation. This case underscores the difficulties in diagnosing, choosing the best treatment, and the importance of clear pediatric guidelines for diagnosing, treating, and preventing relapses in pediatric NMOSD.

1. First episode: In 2023, a 14-year-old girl showed signs of gait ataxia, bilateral lower limb weakness with preserved sensations and bowel/bladder control. Her sensorium was normal, without seizures or vision issues. She had no prior medical concerns. While hospitalised, she underwent surveillance for acute flaccid paralysis, ruling out polio as a cause. EEG showed no significant findings. CSF and serum studies showed no significant findings. MRI Brain and spine not done due to non affordability of the patient's relatives.

The patient received intravenous methylprednisolone for five days, followed by a five-week oral prednisone taper. There was notable improvement in her condition with steroid treatment. Following a one-month inpatient stay with rehabilitation, she was discharged home on a prednisone taper, along with multivitamins and minerals, and continued outpatient rehabilitation.

2. Second episode: Approximately 1 year later, patient presented with a two-week history of right sided progressive paraparesis with paresthesia, eventually leading to complete right sided hemiplegia. Bladder and bowel function was preserved along with intact sensorium and no visual complaints. MRI of the cervical spine was done which showed T2 hyperintensity seen in cervical spine from C2 to C4 with mild cord expansion and patchy peripheral enhancement involving more than 2/3rd of the cord (FIG.1.) This time, the brain MRI showed no abnormalities. Tests for NMO-IgG, AQP4-IgG antibodies in both serum and cerebrospinal fluid (CSF), and CSF oligoclonal bands were negative. Treatment involved intravenous methylprednisolone followed by a gradual oral prednisone taper, along with daily multivitamins and minerals, and limb physiotherapy. After about 15 days of inpatient care, the patient fully regained use of her right-sided upper and lower extremities. Despite being advised further inpatient management; the patient's relatives chose to get discharge against medical advice.

3. Third episode: After 1 month patient again developed gradual onset left sided weakness of upper and lower limbs with no visual complaints, intact sensorium and intact bowel bladder sensations. This eventually progressed to left sided hemiplegia and a history of non compliance to oral medications

was given. MRI brain done was suggestive of small focal area measuring approx. 4 x 3 cm with altered signal intensity in high parietal lobe showing hyperintensity with thin rim of peripheral diffusion restriction and irregular peripheral mild enhancement. (FIG.2.) Cervical MRI had the similar findings as before. Serum and CSF tests for AQP4-IgG, MOG-IgG, and CSF oligoclonal bands were negative. A diagnosis of suspected seronegative NMOSD was established. The patient received high-dose intravenous steroids followed by an oral steroid taper—a five-day course of parenteral steroids followed by oral taper. With one month of comprehensive inpatient treatment and rehabilitation, the patient fully recovered without any residual weakness in the left upper and lower limbs.

FIG.1. MRI of the cervical spine was done which showed T2 hyperintensity seen in cervical spine from C2 to C4.

FIG.2. MRI brain done was suggestive of altered signal intensity in high parietal lobe.

DISCUSSION

NMOSD is an autoimmune disorder that targets the central nervous system, particularly the brain and spinal cord. Initially considered a subtype of multiple sclerosis, the identification of AQP4 autoantibodies revolutionized NMOSD diagnosis.^[1] The 2015 updated diagnostic criteria solidified NMOSD as a separate entity, applicable even in pediatric cases.^[3]

Children diagnosed with NMOSD tend to be older than those with ADEM but have a similar age range to those with MS^[4,2]. Additionally, they have a poorer prognosis compared to MS patients, according to Tillema et al^[5]. In a significant study at the Mayo Clinic, pediatric NMOSD patients had a median onset age of 12 years (range 4–18), with a notable female predominance (88%) and diverse ethnic backgrounds^[4].

The proposed diagnostic criteria for neuromyelitis optica (NMO) in children include optic neuritis, myelitis, and either MRI evidence of a continuous spinal cord lesion spanning three or more segments

or detection of NMO-IgG autoantibody, which binds to the aquaporin-4 (AQP4) water channel and is considered a specific marker for NMO^[7]. NMO-IgG is found in over 70 percent of NMO cases and in a smaller proportion of other demyelinating CNS disorders, such as multiple sclerosis^[8]. Additional involvement of the central nervous system (CNS) beyond the optic nerves and spinal cord is compatible with NMO in patients who meet these criteria^[7].

The clinical progression of NMO varies. It can manifest as a single episode, which may be severe and fatal or lead to different levels of recovery. In pediatric cases, a single episode is common, often resulting in complete neurological recovery^[9,10]. However, some cases exhibit multiple episodes with periods of relapse and remission.

Currently, there are no established protocols for treating NMO. The focus of therapy involves managing acute episodes, preventing complications, and providing rehabilitation. Common medications used include methylprednisolone with prednisone taper, immunosuppressants like azathioprine, cyclophosphamide, and rituximab, as well as plasmapheresis.

CONCLUSION

Diagnosing NMOSD in pediatric patients can be challenging, particularly for those who lack MOG and AQP4 antibodies, leading to uncertainties in treatment selection. Despite this, treatment options for pediatric NMOSD exist and are expected to increase. Recent advancements in understanding NMOSD's neurophysiological mechanisms have led to the investigation of numerous new medications, primarily in adults. However, additional research on the long-term safety and effectiveness of these newer treatments is crucial, especially for seronegative patients. While NMOSD occurrence in children is less frequent than in adults and mainly documented through case reports in the Indian subcontinent, further molecular investigations are essential to accurately differentiate it from other childhood autoimmune disorders^[11,12].

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